

The evaluation of qualitative methods selection in the field of design and emotion

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to aid researchers in selecting appropriate qualitative methods in order to develop and improve future studies in the field of emotional design. These include observations, think-aloud protocols, questionnaires, diaries and interviews. Based on the authors' experiences, it is proposed that the methods under review can be successfully used for collecting data on emotional responses to evaluate user product relationships. This paper reviews the methods; discusses the suitability, advantages and challenges in relation to design and emotion studies. Furthermore, the paper outlines the potential impact of technology on the application of these methods, discusses the implications of these methods for emotion research and concludes with recommendations for future work in this area.

Key words: *emotion design methodologies, emotional design, interaction design.*

1. Introduction

Emotions are an integral part of people's interactions with everyday products. Designers understand that opportunities for innovative products lay in better understanding people, their experiences and how they connect with products on an emotional level. But how do designers begin to uncover and understand this knowledge? The authors propose that applying appropriate qualitative research methods and techniques will lead to a better understanding of people, their experiences and what they value emotionally. Thus, for designers and design researchers it is imperative to identify the effectiveness of particular methods so as to optimize their usefulness in design and emotion research.

In the spirit of recent papers evaluating methods for user experience in design [1,21,18] this paper aims to present a collection of research methods to assist designers and design researchers in selecting the most suitable methods in the study of emotions in design. Further, a discussion and a summary of the advantages and challenges of each method in relation to emotional design research are presented. Although the methods described could be used independently, the authors contend that to study emotions effectively these techniques need to be used together so as to achieve better research rigor and holistic understanding of emotions. It is this approach to evaluating and selecting methodologies that will contribute to further research in the area of design and emotion.

2. The Nature of Emotions

By their very nature emotions are complex and multifaceted. Emotions are implicated in all aspects of daily life including moods, cognition, behavior, attention, perception and memory to name a few [41] and as such, they

influence and affect aspects of everyday activities and interactions between people, the environment and products and artifacts that surround us.

There are several issues regarding emotions that make studying them problematic. First, emotions are subjective and personal, such that two individuals can have completely different about the same event. Second, feelings can be directly and indirectly influenced by the external context, including the environment, time of day, location, weather and social situation among others. Third, an experience can elicit a mixture of emotions that can sometimes be difficult to define. As such attempting to capture and study emotions is a demanding task [21]. In the field of design and emotion methods seeking to study emotional responses pose a challenge for many researchers. Nevertheless the authors argue that issues pertaining to emotions in design can be studied and dealt with to a certain extent. First, utilising qualitative methods is critical in probing and focusing on the intricate and multifaceted nature of emotions. Second, using a combination of methods when studying emotions can assist in identifying and analyzing the complexities of emotional experiences. Third, studying emotions in context as much as possible is fundamental in ascertaining findings that are relevant to designers.

3. Emotions and Qualitative Research

As explained above, due to the very nature of emotions qualitative research methods lend themselves well to studying emotional experiences. Qualitative research is defined by Oliveto [35] as the use of unstructured exploratory techniques to understand a problem in greater depth. Flick [12] points out a qualitative approach acknowledges the complexities of objects and phenomena in real life contexts and does not reduce these complexities to single variables, instead represents them in their entirety in everyday contexts. To try to test and measure emotional issues on a strict quantitative scale may be useful in some cases but to understand emotions in greater depth qualitative research methods must be employed [12].

It is commonly accepted that data collection for product and services evaluation is a central challenge and that novel methodologies must be derived to make any significant contribution to the research field [27,38]. To be innovative, research methods must be created and forged producing an original method for its own unique purpose, to fulfill the study's aims. A gap remains in the existing literature in regards to qualitative method selection from within a design and emotion context. This paper aims to bridge this gap by outlining methods and techniques the authors have employed in previous research studies. These methods include observations, think-aloud protocols, diaries, questionnaires, and interviews. Each method is reviewed and examples of their use in other studies focusing on design and emotion are outlined. Their suitability, advantages and challenges in relation to design and emotion studies is also discussed.

4. Observation

The observation method has been described as a research study where data is collected by watching consumer behaviour or events taking place over a period of time [35]. Observations are originally rooted in ethnographic studies [40] and have more recently been found in the field of design and emotion. Researchers in design and emotion have used observation techniques effectively to gauge a participant's emotional expressions in response to a product stimuli or instructions. Observations are an accepted technique to record emotional responses by analysing

facial expression and verbal content. Observations and the conditions surrounding them can be varied drastically to suite the purpose of each study, as well as the context they are conducted in.

Stanton and Young [49] classify observations into three broad groups; direct, indirect and participant observations. Observations have been useful in recording task sequences and interaction in the field of ergonomics [49,2]. It is from these techniques that the method of the observation has been modified for the design and emotion field. Khalid and Helander [28] measured emotional facial expressions using an observation methodology then analysed the data using a facial action coding system. They matched the different facial expressions to different emotions in response to different interview questions [28]. Jaasko & Mattelmaki [22] used observations to gather in depth, emotional data from participants in understanding the experience of users in hospital laboratories and compared this to the results found using another method. The results showed that observations used in conjunction with another method of data gathering were beneficial in producing emotionally rich data. An observation was also used by Smith & Ellsworth [44] to record facial expressions shown by participants who were describing how they were feeling during different experiences. The subjects recalled past experiences associated with 15 different emotion categories used to produce a model of theory.

Observations have been used by the authors in two distinct studies. Firstly, observations were employed to record raw emotional immediate responses to interactive product stimuli [52]. A variety of products were exposed to participants individually and by using the observation method it was possible to record which immediate response was elicited by each product. Like Smith and Ellsworth [44] the observation was conducted in a laboratory setting and participants were monitored from behind a two-way mirror and an intercom system. Secondly, observations were also employed in a real life environment to capture participant's facial expression to better understand emotional driving experiences [15]. Participants were asked to interact with the interface while driving to perform routine driving tasks including turning on the radio, tuning to a specific radio station, using the front and rear wipers and various other activities. The facial expressions were analysed so as to help determine emotions while performing these tasks in differing driving conditions.

4.1. Advantages

A significant advantage of the observation technique is the fact that the researcher is watching what people do, not simply asking them for their opinion or thoughts. This is especially useful for observing emotions as people can sometimes have difficulty expressing or verbalizing their feelings effectively. Further, utilised in the field, observations capture information from real life contexts, reducing the artificiality common with other techniques [26,40]. Another key advantage identified is the richness and complexity of the data that is obtained. This is particularly advantageous when dealing with emotions since they are complex phenomenons that are difficult to analyse without a rich data set. The data obtained from observations permits the researcher to review and code the data countless times and can be conducted by other researchers, thus improving its reliability.

4.2. Challenges

Ethical issues can arise from involuntarily participation if the element of surprise or unawareness is required [25]. Also, there are concerns regarding the extent to which the observer affects the situation under observation [40] and when emotions are the object of attention there may be uncertainty as to how genuine the emotions may be given the

situation. One way of mitigating this is to conduct the observations in a natural context relating to what you are observing. In addition, in the authors' experience these observations can be time consuming as they require significant effort to conduct and substantial time investment in developing an observation plan or adjusting an existing observation method to suite the study's individual needs. Equipment needed for observations in the experiments included video cameras, microphones, web cameras, laptops and pen and paper and can be costly to obtain and transport to and from the observation site. To mitigate this laboratory with existing data recording instruments could be used. Furthermore the dense and rich data obtained was found to be especially time consuming to sort through and analyse [52]. It was also a challenge to mediate all the random variables that can arise in field observations [15].

5. Think-Aloud Protocol

In conjunction with observations, the think-aloud protocol is a useful method to employ. The reason being that the observation captures the what, while the think-aloud captures the why of an activity. Think-aloud protocols originated in the field of psychology to better understand people's thought processes [47,10]. More recently they have been used regularly in the design disciplines for various purposes including interface evaluations [36,31,23,34] information-seeking analysis of electronic environments [4] as well as research into designer thinking [8,46]. The Think-aloud protocol technique requires a participant to verbalise their thoughts while performing an activity. Ericsson and Simon [10] distinguish between three levels of protocols including vocalisation, verbalisation and retrospective. As the names suggest vocalisation and verbalisation are protocols that are performed *during* a task or activity while retrospective protocols are performed *after* a task being completed [32].

Within the design field, think-aloud protocols have been used to ascertain "users inferences, intuitions, and mental models...reasons...decisions" in an attempt to determine what the participant is thinking throughout an interaction [17:137]. This method is regularly utilised in the human-computer interaction field to test the usability of software-based interfaces. For instance Holzinger [19] conducted an experiment to evaluate an interactive patient communication system at a hospital. In this case the think-aloud protocol was used to help identify the users mental model and interaction of the interface. Further, the terminology used by the user to express ideas or functions provided an opportunity to be incorporated into the system design. Jaspers et al. [23] studied the way in which pediatric oncologists reviewed patient records using the think-aloud protocol method. A cognitive task model was developed from the findings and applied into a new prototype computer interface. Novotny [34] evaluated how web-savvy users searched online catalogues using the think-aloud protocol. The aim was to 'explore not only how users searched the catalog, but also what they were thinking and feeling as they did so' [34: 527].

The above are a few examples of many that demonstrate the application of the think-aloud protocol technique to evaluate and determine usability problems with a device or interface. However, the authors argue that think-aloud protocols can also be used successfully to draw out issues pertaining to emotions during interactions. The think-aloud protocol technique has potential for use in exploring broader and more complex issues of interaction [32,40], which include emotions. Gomez at al [15] conducted an experiment utilising a think-aloud protocol investigating the emotional experience of driving. Participants were required to drive around a specified route while they performed specific tasks with the vehicle dashboard. They were asked to verbalise their emotional reactions during interaction with the interface. The think-aloud protocol (in conjunction with the observation technique) was effectively used to

identify the elements and the reasons why the vehicle interface impacted the emotional experience while driving in a positive or negative manner.

5.1. Advantages

The think-aloud protocol was useful in drawing out the emotional reaction of the participant as they performed the activities [15]. This method provides rich qualitative data useful for analysing deeper and more complex issues regarding emotion. As Branch [4] highlights, 'for qualitative researchers interested in getting a rich source of data, the verbal protocol analysis method is an excellent choice' [4: 374]. An unexpected benefit of using this technique was that participants began to comment in-between activities, providing further explanations for their emotional reactions, ultimately offering a more holistic verbalisation of their emotions than initially envisioned.

5.2. Challenges

Although the think-aloud protocol elicited an abundant amount of useful data in some instances participants reverted to simply verbalising their actions rather than their emotions. On these occasions it is important to prompt the participant to express their emotions as they could easily regress to simply explaining the *what* of their interactions rather than the *why*. Another element to consider is the equipment required to record the think-aloud protocol. A video camera was used successfully in the authors' case to capture both audio and video footage [15]. Nonetheless, depending on the context, an audio and a video recorder might be needed to capture both audio and video data. Another drawback of the think-aloud protocol is that it may cause added distraction to the participant while they are trying to perform a task causing unnecessary cognitive load [32,4]. It has also been noted that participants may find it difficult to speak when the task becomes demanding, resulting in silence during the time when the researcher is most interested in obtaining information [37]. One way to get around this is to prompt the participant to continue verbalising their thoughts. Another is to make sure that more than one method is being applied to record the participant's activities during the experiment. Notwithstanding, these disadvantages need to be weighed against the promising results the method can provide.

6. Questionnaire

Similar to the think-aloud protocol, the questionnaire can also assist in identifying not just the *what* of a product interaction but also the *why*. Oliveto [35] describes a questionnaire as a structured method for collecting data consisting of a series of questions. Questionnaires can be self-completed or administered by an interviewer and can also be completed orally or in writing [35]. Jordan [26] identifies two types of questionnaires; fixed response and open-ended questionnaires. They are especially useful for rapid collection of large amounts of data from large population samples [48].

The current use of the questionnaire is highly instrumental, undertaken especially in the areas of marketing and psychology but more recently has been applied in the field of design and emotion. Pre-selection questionnaires or screening questionnaires can be used to assess if participants meet all the requirements for the study, from age demographics to how emotionally expressive they are [44]. Open-ended questionnaires can be used to pre-empt responses and emotional data before the second part of the methodology is introduced such as an observation or interview [6]. Seva, Duh & Helander [42] applied a closed questionnaire which tested 60 participants using an emotional scale to gauge the pre-purchase effect of a sample of products. Questionnaires can also be applied after an

experiment to gauge participants' responses and assess ratings on experienced emotions in regards to what they just observed or experienced in the prior experiment [29]. The screening questionnaire was used by the author [52] to obtain participant's demographic information as well as establish suitability for the study by asking questions relating to product ownership. Those that qualified for the study were asked to partake further and continue with the overall experiment.

6.1. Advantages

The main advantage of the questionnaire method from experience is the standardised format of responses permits objectivity and consistency, reducing bias. It was also found to be relatively quick to collect a large amount of data; however this can depend on the study and the sample size being targeted. Notwithstanding, the potential exists to collect data from a large pool of participants and analyse it quickly [51]. Questionnaires were very time and cost effective when compared to face-to-face interviews. This is especially true for studies involving large sample sizes and large geographic areas. Emailed or electronic questionnaires have become even more time and cost effective as they are sent and received instantaneously via the internet. Further, they were found to be less intrusive than telephone or face-to-face surveys. For instance, when a respondent receives a questionnaire in the mail, they are free to complete it in their own time. Unlike other research methods, the respondent is not interrupted by the research instrument [9].

6.2. Challenges

A challenge experienced with the questionnaire method is when conducted after the event participants may forget important issues related to the task. If the questionnaire is open-ended the questions may generate large amounts of data that can take a long time to process and analyse. One way of limiting this would be to limit the space available on the response sheet. A further challenge can be that participants may answer superficially especially if the questionnaire takes a long time to complete [25]. Asking too many questions should also be avoided because it can lead to inaccurate responses. Moreover participants may not wish to reveal any information for fear of being ridiculed by giving their real opinion. To alleviate this, participants should be told why the information is being collected and how the results will be beneficial. They should be asked to reply honestly and told that a negative response is just as acceptable as a positive response. To further assist in these situations the questionnaire should be made anonymous where possible [38].

7. Diaries

Diaries are research instruments used to examine and explore ongoing experiences within everyday situations. The fundamental strength of diaries is that they allow the capture of changes and patterns of experiences in natural contexts and help in determining the factors that affect this change [3]. This is especially relevant for the area of design and emotion, where the attempt is to study people's emotional experience within everyday and ongoing contexts.

Various aspects of interaction have been the focus of study in design ranging from people's informal use of computers in the workplace [39] through to exploring the use of mobile technology in everyday settings [45]. However, more innovative approaches to the typical diary designs have been implemented in design research since the publication of Gaver, Dunne and Pacenti's [13] paper; Cultural Probes. Gaver et al. [13] introduced a novel

technique to conceptualise data collection by providing participants with packs (or what they term ‘cultural probes’) consisting of postcards, maps, a camera, a photo album and a media diary. The aim of their study was to elicit inspirational responses from elderly people regarding the communities in which they lived. The critical difference with the approach was the move away from a structured and scientific diary design to a more unstructured, exploratory approach for accessing information from people. As Gaver et al. [13] point out ‘Unlike much research, we don’t emphasise precise analyses or carefully controlled methodologies; instead, we concentrate on aesthetic control, the cultural implications of our designs, and ways to open new spaces for design’ [13: 24]. Gaver et al.’s approach is compatible with the study of emotional aspect in design as it focuses on the qualitative and aesthetic aspects of people and their experiences in natural contexts.

Since their study, Gaver et al.’s approach to diaries has generated a host of similar studies in the design field, focusing specifically on issues relating to emotional experiences of people in their everyday lives. Mattelmaki and Battarbee [30] explored the use of what they termed ‘empathy probes’ to study people’s exercise routine in everyday life contexts. The empathy probe packs consisted of diaries alongside disposable cameras, maps, stickers and postcards. The aim was to study well-being and exercise, focusing mainly on the emotions, thoughts and feeling regarding these experiences. Likewise Crabtree et al. [5] conducted a study using modified cultural probes to explore computer support for former psychiatric patients living in residential care settings. Wensveen, Overbeeke and Djajadiningrat [50] utilised a diary technique as the central part of an adapted cultural probe targeting emotionally rich interactions through the design of an alarm clock. Participants were required to mark images of facial expressions on the diary indicating how they felt about waking up, their plans for the day and how their day has been.

These are some examples of how diaries have been used in design successfully to study emotional experiences of interaction. The authors of this paper [15] conducted a study using a diary to explore the emotional experience of interaction with portable devices including mp3 players and personal digital assistants over six months. The diaries were used by participants to record relevant interactions with the products and the resulting emotional perception of that interaction. The structure of the diary provided participants the liberty to include up to three emotional experiences per week. The question on the diary were structured and asked about the context of interaction, the activity performed, who was present during interactions and a summary of their perception of the emotional experience (perceived emotional reaction to experience). The participants recorded the overall emotional experience using an Emotional Chart [15].

7.1. Advantages

From the author’s experience the most significant benefit of diaries is that they provide very rich and comprehensive information regarding people’s emotional experiences while interacting with products in everyday life [15]. Mattelmaki and Battarbee [30] propose that “some personal issues are easier to write than say aloud” [30: 268] and thus the diary technique provides this particular advantage over other verbal techniques. Additionally the diaries were useful in gaining information regarding the contextual and situational factors pertaining to those experiences. It was critical to observe the changes and variation of the emotional experience over the course of six months and the diary technique was effective in capturing this change. Diaries are very flexible in how they are designed and as such can be successfully used to focus the participant’s response specifically on the emotional aspects of the

interactions.

7.2. Challenges

From experience the main challenge of the diary technique is the large amount of responsibility placed on the participant to continually and reliably fill out the diary over an extended period of time. As Bolger et al [3] highlights 'in order to obtain reliable and valid data, diary studies must achieve a level of participant commitment and dedication rarely required in other types of research studies. The burden of repeated queries and responses places substantial demands on the participant.' [4: 591-592]. To complicate the issue, the more unstructured the diary design becomes the more this particular problem is exacerbated. One way to mitigate this is to make the diary design more rigid (thus more efficient from the participant's point of view) so the participant is not required to spend too much time thinking about what to write. Further, it is imperative to invest some time in keeping an open channel of communication with the participant over the period of investigation. This will achieve two outcomes; provide the participant an avenue to ask the researcher any questions they may have about filling out the diary, and keep the momentum of the participant going forward.

8. Interview

Interviews are founded on the idea of conversations and as a research method they generally involve a face-to-face discussion between two people guided by a set of pre-determined questions [16]. The social sciences have a long history of utilising interview methods for a variety of purposes [40,16]. The flexibility of the interview method allows it to be applied in many circumstances and as such has been used to investigate a range of topics in the design sphere including usability concerns, user attitudes, perceptions and reactions, error rates and other aspects of user-product interaction [48].

Interviews are generally characterised as structured, semi-structured or unstructured [40]. A structured interview is effectively a questionnaire with a highly structured format and the possible responses are limited. In a semi-structured interview the questions are more open and less controlled and the participant has much more flexibility in their responses. Finally, an unstructured interview is a free-flowing conversation based around the general topic of the interview [37]. Structured interviews are useful when the aims of the study are well established. They are particularly valuable if time is a concern as they can be performed quickly and methodically. On the other hand unstructured and semi-structured interviews can often take time to perform but generate rich and complex data [37]. As a result semi-structured and unstructured interviews have been effectively used in the field of design to explore questions relating to people's thoughts, beliefs, attitudes and emotional feelings on design. For instance Desmet, Overbeeke and Tax [7] conducted a study to design products with added emotional value. In this study a technique termed as 'emocard interview' was conducted to assess the emotional response to existing mobile phone designs. This was followed by an unstructured interview where participant's attitudes and use of mobile phones were discussed. In another study Hirsch et al [20] explored the experiences of elders and their caregivers by conducting lifestyle interviews in the participant's homes. The aim was to assess the importance of psychological and social factors in the eldercare environment so as to identify implications for product interface and interaction design opportunities.

The examples above highlight the effectiveness of interviews in exploring issues relating to emotions in design. The

authors of this paper also used interviews to explore emotional issues pertaining to product interaction. In one study the emotional experience with portable interactive devices was investigated [15]. Part of the study involved conducting semi-structured interviews intermittently with participants over a six-month period. Participants were asked about their use of the product, to discuss the positive and negative experiences with the product and to reflect whether the context of use influenced the emotional experience of interaction. The interview technique allowed for interesting aspects relating to the emotional experience of interacting with portable devices to be captured. In another study semi-structured interviews were utilised to study the emotional experience of driving in a real driving situation [15]. Specifically, the interviews were used to assist in gauging the subjective emotional state of the participant before and after the driving experience. The intent was to determine how and what part of the driving activity influenced the emotional experience in a positive or negative manner.

8.1. Advantages

The main strength of the interview method is that the researcher has control of the pace and direction of the line of inquiry and gives the flexibility to follow interesting comments that may emerge during the interview itself [40]. In the authors experience the semi-structured interview was beneficial as this permitted the researcher to keep the conversation focused and also provided the flexibility for asking pointed questions on issues pertaining to emotions. Further, the semi-structured method gave the participant the necessary scope to reflect and discuss deeper issues relevant to their emotional experiences, which would have been difficult to capture in a more structured, pre-determined interview or questionnaire method. A further benefit of interviewing is that it can elicit very rich and meaningful information due to the face-to-face and one-on-one nature of the technique. If performed with care the interview will permit the participant to feel comfortable and more willingly discuss issues at length and in more detail than an impersonal questionnaire or form. The equipment needed for recording is generally not expensive either. If notes are being taken then very little equipment is required. If audio is being recorded a tape recorder of some description may be necessary.

8.2. Challenges

Fundamentally, perhaps the biggest drawback of the interview method is the fact that what people say and what they do can be different [43]. Thus, relying solely on interview information for accessing the complete story about people's real-world activities is problematic. Interviews are most useful when used in conjunction with other techniques [40]. Accurately recording interviews can present various difficulties also. If note taking is to be performed as the interview is taking place an experienced researcher is required as it can be easy to make mistakes or fail to record important information. Recording the interviews using audiotape can assist in this instance as the researcher has the luxury to engage the participant more directly without the need to divide time between asking questions, having a conversation and taking notes simultaneously. There is also a permanent record for the researcher to come back to at any point in time for review. In the authors experience a combination of audio-taping and note taking was advantageous as this combined the benefits of taking notes of the most interesting parts of the interview while not dismissing what might seem trivial at the time through the audio recording [43,40]. Another challenge is that interviews can be time-consuming to perform and to analyse.

9. Summary of Qualitative Methods

All qualitative methods reported in this paper have various advantages depending on the study's purpose. There are

also various challenges that in some cases can be mitigated or preempted. Table 1 summarises the method techniques in detail discussed in this paper.

Table 1: Method Summary

Methodology	Description	Recording Method	Advantages	Challenges
Observation	Watching behaviour or events take place over a period of time in the field or in a lab setting	Video Audio Notes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watching people's actual behaviour • Rich, comprehensive and intricate data • Visual and verbal data • Real time recording • Repeated playback and can be analysed by others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical issues with the observer affecting the result • Time consuming to analyse • Costly • Equipment
Think – Aloud protocol	Participants verbalise thoughts while performing an activity	Video Audio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich data • Holistic verbalisation of emotional reaction • Easy to perform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tendency for action verbalisation rather than thoughts • Equipment can be substantial • Cognitive load
Questionnaire	A structured list of questions for submitted for replies that is used for collecting data	Text Audio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised procedure eliminating bias • Quick to test a large number of participants • Cost effective • Minimal intrusion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validity of data post event recollection • Open-ended questionnaires mass amounts of data to analyse • Reluctant to reveal some emotional content as it is recorded
Diaries	Record behavior, thoughts, feelings and emotions in a journal over time	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich and comprehensive data of experience over time • Can record change and variations over time in emotional response • Some issues are easier to write than talk about • Record context and situational factors • Can be performed at the pace of participant • Inexpensive and quick to distribute • Easy to use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time consuming to analyse • High level of participant commitment
Interview	A conversation between two people guided by a set of pre-determined questions	Audio Video Notes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher has control of pace and direction of inquiry • (Semi-structured) Flexibility for participant to explain thoughts, feelings, emotions • Rich and meaningful data • Permits issues to be discussed at length • Minimal equipment required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What people say may not always be what they do (note-taking) Important information can be left out or not recorded • Time consuming to perform and analyse

9. Discussion and Implications

This paper and the methods discussed is a reflective evaluation of the authors experiences with qualitative methods and techniques applied to studies in the design and emotion field of research. Additionally the authors also recommend that more than one method be chosen to complete the research design. A culmination of 2-3 different methods was decided upon in the various research studies previously conducted by the authors [15,51,52]. Triangulation is imperative to research design due to the nature of emotions. It facilitates validation of data through cross verification from more than two sources and increases the credibility and validity of the results [40], thus creating more effective methods and utilizing their advantages in design and emotion research.

The authors are currently working on applying the methods outlined in this paper to a product interaction timeline in order to enable designers and researchers in this field identify when and how each method should be used. This will provide a platform for selecting the techniques in combination or independently in order to satisfy the requirements of the research. The intent is to provide a benchmark in methodology selection in the field of design and emotion

research.

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